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Library and Information Services of A.C. Joshi Library during COVID – 19 pandemic: a study of faculty satisfaction

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Abstract

The ongoing pandemic is a global challenge that has resulted in significant morbidity and mortality worldwide. It has severely affected the economy and social integrity of most of the nations. Everyone who has lived through this period of uncertainty has acknowledged the fact that these circumstances have changed the way of life of people across the globe. While there has been a rising concern about the severity of the health challenges faced by the general population, especially vulnerable is the situation of the elderly, the children, health professionals, and also academicians who are braving the mal-effects of this grave onslaught that is a threat to mankind's very existence. The teaching fraternity is constantly facing the negative effect of information deprivation due to the closure of libraries and overload through available technologies. The focus of this study is to understand the problems of stress and dissatisfaction experienced by the academicians at Panjab University, Chandigarh (India) during and post lockdown COVID-19 pandemic. The classic empirical mixed-method approach was used for data collection by using quantitative and qualitative techniques. A structured questionnaire and in-depth interviews were conducted to obtain views of the teaching fraternity. The study highlights various mental stress challenges experienced by teaching fraternity and how libraries have been coming to the forefront to maintain a strategic equilibrium and balance between mind and body during the pandemic. The findings could have tremendous scope for other studies on the subject as well as evolving policy implications.

Keywords

Teachers, Online learning, University libraries, User satisfaction, Technology-led strategy, Mental stress, Coping pandemic

1. Introduction

COVID-19 has proven to be a ruthless contagion that spread from Wuhan City of China's Hubei province in December 2019 and developed into a full blown global crisis by spreading over more than 200 countries of the globe with disastrous outcomes. The infection has been suspected to be passed from one person to another through viruses. It has been presented through a range of symptoms including fever, dry cough, shortness of breath and breathing difficulties, tiredness with possible symptoms of aches and pains, nasal congestion, running nose, sore throat and diarrhoea resulting in total weakness and even death (World Health Organization, 2020a). Many countries have demonstrated astute leadership by implementing emergency measures to prevent the infectious spread.

In this context, the lockdown strategy of India swung into immediate action as schools, universities, cinemas, museums, restaurants along with all places of public gathering like transport systems, work places, area of congregation (whether religious or otherwise) were all shut down. All human interaction-social, economic, political or otherwise was closed. Socio-cultural events were cancelled indefinitely as people were being quarantined after travel within or outside the country for work or pleasure. Several travel restrictions, closed borders protocols and cancelled flights from and to countries with a high level of contamination (as in India, Canada, China, Italy, France, Spain, US and several others) were observed. The entire world seemed to have come to a standstill. It has been observed that during this outbreak, there have been undercurrents of increasing mental and socio-psychological issues afflicting people belonging to all walks of life (Duan and Zhu 2020; Chen et al. 2020; Liem et al. 2020 and Yang et al. 2020). It is a fairly significant observation that no specific recommendations have been made from any international body regarding addressing of such issues during the pandemic.

1.1 Emerging Mental Health Issues in COVID-19 Pandemic

The main psychological impact of the situation is the elevated rates of stress and anxiety that may have been induced by levels of loneliness, responsibilities and worry besides lack of fruitful activity. A recent study of 1210 participants from 194 cities in China reportedly showed that 53.8 percent of participants exhibited moderate or severe psychological impact, while 31.3 percent showed signs of some sort of depression, 36.4 percent had bouts of anxiety and 32.4 percent were experiencing bouts of stress (Liu et al. 2020).

Studies have shown that isolated or quarantined people had suffered anxiety and guilt as an aftermath of the contagion which was observed to have a spilling effect as stigma being attached to the family members and friends (Wang et al. 2020). Some studies which PTSD (Post-Traumatic Stress Disorder) to be a precursor to the depression experienced by family members and close contacts (Goyal et al. 2020). Certain studies have reported that physicians and especially Frontline Health Care Providers (FHCP) comprising personnel ranking among paramedics, ambulance personnel and other health care delivery practitioners have shown symptoms and signs of

heightened stress, emotional disturbances and behavioral aberrations from their normal temperament as being indicative of higher levels of depression and anxiety (Goyal et al. 2020).

Thus, the rapidly spreading pandemic carries in its wake a considerable degree of fear, worry and concern for various groups particularly among the older adults and people having other forms of comorbid disorders (Dong and Bouey, 2020). There is also the contention that the potential impact of the existing ill-health conditions could probably lead to psychiatric symptoms that are somehow related to the interplay of mental disorders and immunity (World Health Organization, 2020b).

1.2 Stress in adapting to newer learning teaching technologies and role of libraries

Looking at the available literature about the impact on different fractions of population like infected patients, their close contacts, the elderly, the infants and children as well as the health professionals, it was realized that teaching professionals were also facing similar level of stress induced hardships and were prone to gradually losing control. The challenges for the academicians are rooted in their ability to adept technical (how to teach from a distance), emotional (constantly devise means for coping with new situation) and the pedagogical knowledge (finding methodology for good quality teaching). Most teaching fraternity had to adapt to a fast paced world of online education methodologies because nearly 90 per cent of all learners were away from schools and institutions of higher education (Falt, 2020). Most teachers and their organizations had to reconcile themselves to rise to the challenge. They had to adapt themselves to teaching learning technologies and familiarize themselves to the tasks of innovative teaching methodologies at a very fast pace. It was almost a transformative metamorphosis for them from using one platform of teaching to others including Zoom, Google Meet, Cisco WebEx, Skype, Google Duo, etc.

The immense transition to online learning has forced the academic libraries to serve their clients via remote login to maintain social distancing. All around the world, libraries have been working hard to provide remote access of their collections and have put their best efforts to upgrade their websites to comply with the demand of their users. Although several libraries already had a strong digital presence, many others have now moved to build one in order to continue serving patrons during the pandemic. Publishers have also risen to the occasion by offering more and more free content and curating personalized collections so that academicians can continue to read and teach without disruption. Indeed, as the demand for credible e-resources surges, libraries have emerged as vital pathway to high quality e-books, journals and educational content. As highlighted in a survey by the Conference of Directors of National Libraries around the globe, $\frac{3}{4}$ of national libraries had introduced new digital services (CDNL 2019 and the Next Generation, 2019). For example, in India, Kota Public Library has increased its online services, promoting bibliotherapy as a means of helping users through the crisis, and receiving useful coverage in the local press. The National Library of Medicine in United States is maintaining an electronic collection with a strong focus on dealing with stress and worry, and promoting positive mental health. Similarly, academic libraries are making all possible efforts to provide remote access, online article request service, conducting webinars and panel discussions on all the topical issues and are

working as a catalyst for effective dissemination of information to reduce the stress of academicians (COVID-19 and the Global Library Field, 2020).

The current research work is an effort to study how the academicians at Panjab University, Chandigarh (India) are facing the emerging challenges of teaching in online environment as also how Internet and A.C. Joshi Library through its remote logins and direct publisher-access privilege has come to their rescue in combating all forms of academic stress including the techno stress.

1.3 Brief Profile of Panjab University, Chandigarh (India) and Central Library

The Panjab University (PU), established in 1882 as University of Punjab at Lahore is one of the oldest Universities in India. It has 78 teaching and research departments and 15 Centers/Chairs which are actively engaged in collaborative research projects with various other institutions at national and international level. It has achieved 2nd Rank in the Atal Ranking of Institutions on Innovation Achievements (ARIIA) amongst Indian Universities as declared by Ministry of Education, Govt. of India in 2020 (<http://puchd.ac.in/pu-profile.php>). The central library of the university, officially known as “A.C. Joshi Library” is equipped with modern facilities and resources (both print and electronic). It has rich collection of approximately 9 lakh documents in hard copy form including books, theses/dissertations, manuscripts, rare books, government reports, back files of newspapers and bound volumes of journals. The library has subscription of more than 25 databases, 483 e-books and 5000 full text e-journals. The library has gone beyond its four walls during the pandemic and provided access to its collection and resources through RemoteXs services including Bloomas Literature (Infobase Trial), McGrawHill E-books, CREDO Reference (Reference Sources), EBSCO COVID-19 Resources, etc (<https://library.puchd.ac.in/digital-library.php>).

2. Research Methodology

With the objective of accessing data inputs on various aspects of stress involved in dealing with newer systems of learning and teaching on the part of the academicians, research methodology that comprised the dual approach of quantitative and qualitative analysis was adopted. Quantitative data was collected using an online (anonymous) survey platform (Google Forms) in keeping with the Indian Government’s recommendations to minimize face-to-face or physical interaction as everyone continued to isolate themselves at home. Teaching fraternity of various departments from life-sciences, social sciences, languages, design and fine-arts, engineering technology, business school, multidisciplinary departments, etc, of P.U. were administered questionnaires and interview guides through text messages, e-mails and WhatsApp chats. The study was conducted during the complete lockdown and post lockdown period being observed in the country (i.e., from 1st April 2020 to 31st August 2020). A total 152 faculty members responded to the questionnaire and over 55 members participated in telephonic in-depth interviews for obtaining qualitative inputs.

2.1 Study Questionnaire

The modus operandi used was that once the teaching faculty had clicked on the link, they were given information about the nature and purpose of the survey on the first page. Subsequently, they were guided to the next page (first section) of the survey. The first part of the questionnaire was focused on collecting socio-demographic information pertaining to the name, age, gender, designation, department of teaching subjects taught, etc. The second part of the survey was designed to gather information on how much time they were devoting to Internet usage, what were the resources being searched for and used as well as what was their level of comprehension and satisfaction on the initiatives being taken by A.C. Joshi Library as also what were their further expectations for the near future. For the qualitative inputs, the interviews were conducted with the help of an interview guide and cue cards to avoid digressing from the topic.

3. Research Findings

3.1 Quantitative Analysis

The data collected through the survey was tabulated and analyzed using MS Excel and SPSS software. The results and findings for quantitative data are given below:

3.1.1 Demographics

Sr. No.	Demographic Features		Number	Percentage
1.	Gender	Male	72	47.37%
		Female	80	52.63%
2.	Age	30-40yrs	51	33.55%
		40-50yrs	64	42.11%
		50-60yrs	25	16.45%
		60 and above	12	07.89%
3.	Designation	Assistant Professor	77	50.66%
		Associate Professor	21	13.82%
		Professor	54	35.52%
4.	Discipline	Sciences	79	51.97%
		Social Sciences	73	48.03%

Table-1: Demographic Profile of Survey Respondents

The demographic profile of the respondents in the survey is shown in Table-1 which indicates that 47 percent males and 53 percent females participated in the survey. The respondents were distributed across a wide range of age categories. The largest proportion of respondents were in the age category of 40 to 50 year (42 percent), 34 percent were in the age category of 30-40 years, while 17 percent were in the age category of 50 to 60 years. In fact, 8 percent respondents belonged to the age category of 60 years and above. According to the designation of the faculty, they were Assistant Professors (51 Percent), Associate Professors (14 Percent) and Professors (36 percent).

With respect to their discipline, almost 52 percent respondents were from science stream and 48 percent were from the social sciences.

3.1.2 Time devoted online per day for teaching, learning and reading

The respondents in the survey were asked about the time they spent online for teaching, learning and reading on a daily basis. The results are shown in table below:

Designation	Time Duration				
	1-2 hrs	2-3 hrs	3-4 hrs	4-5 hrs	More than 5 hrs
Assistant Professor	5 (6.4)	19 (11.7)	22 (28.6)	17 (22.1)	14 (18.2)
Associate Professor	3 (14.3)	7 (33.3)	3 (14.3)	6 (28.6)	2 (9.5)
Professor	6 (11.1)	15 (27.7)	14 (25.9)	12 (22.2)	7 (12.9)

Note: Percentage in parenthesis.

Table-2: Time Devoted Online per day for Teaching, Learning and Reading

The responses in Table-2 shows that among the Assistant Professors, 28.6 percent spent 3-4 hours every day on teaching, learning and reading with the help of online facilities, 22.1 percent spent 4-5 hours and 18 percent spent more than 5 hours a day, 11.7 percent spent 2-3 hours and just about 6 percent spent less than 1 to 2 hours on this exercise. Among the Associate Professors, the maximum proportion (33 percent) spent 2-3 hours, 28.6 percent spent 4-5 hours, 14 percent spent less than 2 hours and 3-4 hours on an average respectively, 9.5 percent spent over 5 hours a day on teaching, learning and reading their subject on the Internet. Among the Professors, 27.7 percent spent 2-3 hours on teaching learning, 25.9 percent spent 3-4 hours, and 22 percent spent 4-5 years in this pursuit. There were 12.9 percent Professors who spent 5 hours or more in updating themselves and 11.1 percent spent under an hour.

Thus, it can be deduced that all faculty members were spending large quantity of time upgrading their knowledge levels to constantly be prepared to adopt and adapt themselves to the new emerging technologies and coping with the kind of techno stress. The greatest chunk of respondents was spending 3-4 hours on a daily basis to adapt themselves to the new and changed environment of teaching and learning.

3.1.3 Online resources accessed for study inputs

The respondents in the survey were further asked on the kinds of resources they were constantly accessing for their study inputs currently. Their responses have been depicted in Figure-1 below:

Figure-1: Online Resources Accessed for Study Inputs

All respondents gave more than one response about the usage of resources during COVID-19 pandemic. Figure-1 indicates that 90.9 percent Assistant Professors used websites as a chief resource, 79.2 percent used e-books, 75.3 percent used e-journals, 54.5 percent used online tutorials and 12.9 percent read blogs for gathering information.

Among the Associate Professors also, the trends were almost the same as 95.2 percent accessed websites, but their reference to e-books and e-journals was equal at 80.9 percent and their use of online tutorials (42.9 percent) and blogs (28.6 percent) was also similar. Among the Professors, there was considerably lesser use of Internet resources as 92.5 percent used websites and 77.7 percent reportedly used e-journals, 66.6 percent preferred e-books and 35.2 percent used online tutorials, besides 20.4 percent found blogs useful for their information needs.

3.1.4 Information about resources of A.C. Joshi Library

The comments on the information received were gathered in the qualitative narratives. When the faculty was asked about how they received information about the information sources and services being offered and provided by the A.C. Joshi Library, the survey respondents gave the answers given in Figure-2. The largest source of information was through e-mails sent periodically by the Librarian through the computer center.

Figure-2: Information about resources of A.C. Joshi Library

Figure-2 clearly depicts that 52.4 percent Associate Professors reported that they got information from other fellow colleagues and 71.4 percent received e-mails from the Director, Computer Centre sent by the library for circulation among faculties and 33.3 percent found information on their social media groups. Among the Assistant Professors, 83.1 percent received e-mails from the Director of the Computer Centre, while 32.5 percent were informed by fellow professionals and 25.9 percent received information from the social media. Among the Professors, 81.5 percent received e-mails from the Director, Computer Centre; 35.2 percent from the social media and 31.5 percent from fellow colleagues. Thus, the emails from Director, Computer Centre performed a yeoman service by rapidly updating the teachers on the latest inputs on online resources and services given by A.C. Joshi Library.

3.1.5 Resource Offered by the Library and Being Used Commonly

The respondents in the survey were further asked about the resources offered by the library which they were constantly accessing for their study inputs currently. Their responses have been depicted in Table-3 below:

Sources of Information	Designation		
	Assistant Professor n(%)	Associate Professor n(%)	Professor n(%)
Bloomas Literature (Infobase Trial)	2 (2.6)	1 (4.7)	2 (3.7)
SCOPUS	55 (71.4)	10 (47.6)	30 (55.5)
Springer Nature E-Book Collection	46 (59.7)	7 (33.3)	23 (42.5)
McGrawHill E-books	32	8	26

	(41.6)	(38.1)	(48.1)
Science Direct Resources	50 (64.9)	7 (33.3)	30 (55.5)
e-Shodh Sindhu Resources	25 (32.5)	4 (19.0)	22 (40.7)
Emerald subscriptions through OAN	10 (12.9)	4 (19.0)	9 (16.6)
CREDO Reference (Reference Sources)	7 (9.0)	0 (0.0)	5 (9.3)
Proquest Theses and Dissertations (PQDT)	11 (14.3)	5 (23.8)	14 (25.9)

Note: Percentage in parenthesis.

Table-3: Resource Used Commonly

The responses on what was being used most commonly by the faculty as a library resource represented in Table-3 indicates that SCOPUS was mostly commonly searched followed by Springer Nature-E Book Collection and McGraw Hill e-books. After these, there were Science Direct Resources, E-Shodh Sindhu Resources and Emerald Transcriptions through OAN as well as CREDO Reference. It is interesting to note that Bloomas Literature (Infobase Trial) was the last on the list of Professors and Assistant Professors, while the Associate Professors never used it. Thus, the teaching faculty became well acquainted with the common library resources in a very short period of time.

3.1.6 Rating of A.C. Joshi Library Efforts in Providing Resources and Services through RemoteXs

The respondents were further asked to rate on the scale of 1-5 (i.e., not at all effective to extremely effective) the efforts of A.C. Joshi Library in providing electronic resources and services through RemoteXs platform during COVID-19 pandemic.

Designation	Level of effectiveness										Chi-Square and p-value
	Not Effective		Slightly effective		Somewhat effective		Moderately effective		Extremely effective		
	(n)	(%)	(n)	(%)	(n)	(%)	(n)	(%)	(n)	(%)	
Assistant Professor	1	1.3	5	6.5	11	14.3	36	46.8	24	31.2	<i>p-value</i> 0.579
Associate Professor	1	4.8	1	4.8	5	23.8	7	33.3	7	33.3	
Professor	1	1.9	2	3.7	16	29.6	22	40.7	13	24.0	

Table-4: Rating of A.C. Joshi Library Efforts in Providing Resources and Services through RemoteXs

It is interesting to note from the Table-4 above that the largest proportion of the responses were for moderately effective, followed by extremely effective and somewhat effective. There were a small proportion of the responses for ineffective and slightly effective. The greatest proportion of the Assistant Professors was inclined towards finding the A.C. Joshi Library resources and services through RemoteXs to be adequate and largely effective. This was true for the Associate Professors as also the Professors. The Chi-square values and p-value in the above Table-4 show the availability of the resources of the A.C. Joshi Library to be available effectively across a cross-section of the academicians.

The rating of A.C. Joshi Library's efforts in providing resources and services through RemoteXs platform during COVID-19 pandemic has been accessed on discipline wise criteria also, as depicted in Table-5 below:

Discipline	Level of effectiveness									
	Not Effective		Slightly effective		Somewhat effective		Moderately effective		Extremely effective	
	(n)	(%)	(n)	(%)	(n)	(%)	(n)	(%)	(n)	(%)
Social Sciences	1	1.4	5	6.9	17	23.3	25	34.2	25	34.2
Sciences	2	2.5	3	3.8	15	18.9	40	50.6	19	24.0

Table-5: Level of Effectiveness across disciplines

To test the difference (if any) in A.C. Joshi Library's efforts in providing resources and services through RemoteXs among the science and social science disciplines, independent sample *t*-test has been applied as depicted in Table-6 below. In the first stage, Library's efforts (RemoteXs service) for both the disciplines were subjected to *t*-test, homogeneity of variances was assumed based on the Levene's test. Results show no significant difference in the efforts by library for social sciences and sciences discipline $t(150) = .214, p > 0.05$.

Discipline	n	Mean	SD	t-cal	df	p
Social Science	73	3.93	0.991	0.214	150	.149
Science	79	3.90	0.900			

Table-6: *t*-test results for A.C. Joshi Library's RemoteXs Service across discipline

3.1.7 Level of satisfaction with Availability of Resources for Teaching-Learning under Current Circumstances

Designation	Level of satisfaction										Chi-Square and p-value
	Not at all satisfied		Slightly satisfied		Moderately satisfied		Very satisfied		Extremely satisfied		
	(n)	(%)	(n)	(%)	(n)	(%)	(n)	(%)	(n)	(%)	
Assistant Professor	1	1.3	3	3.9	18	23.4	37	48.0	18	23.4	6.34 <i>p value</i> 0.609
Associate Professor	0	0	2	9.5	7	33.3	7	33.3	5	23.8	
Professor	1	1.9	4	7.4	7	13.0	26	48.1	16	29.6	

Table-7: Level of satisfaction with Availability of Resources for Teaching-Learning under Current Circumstances

When asked to measure the level of satisfaction with the newer patterns of getting library resources under the current circumstances, the larger proportion of responses were for either very satisfied or extremely satisfied as indicated in Table-7 above. The Assistant Professors were either very satisfied or extremely satisfied, while the Associate Professors were moderately satisfied and very satisfied and the Professors were also very satisfied and extremely satisfied. Thus, overall the faculty members were totally satisfied with the availability of the teaching and learning e-resources being provided by the A.C. Joshi Library, Panjab University. The value of the Chi-square and p-value tests shows that the level of satisfaction with the variant of forms of resources and services of library was almost equal for all academicians.

The level of satisfaction with the availability of various e-resources for teaching-learning has been evaluated among the different disciplines i.e., social science and science also, as represented in Table-8 below:

Discipline	Level of satisfaction									
	Not at all satisfied		Slightly satisfied		Moderately satisfied		Very satisfied		Extremely satisfied	
	(n)	(%)	(n)	(%)	(n)	(%)	(n)	(%)	(n)	(%)
Social Sciences	1	1.4	4	5.5	22	30.1	27	37.0	19	26.0
Sciences	1	1.3	5	6.3	10	12.7	43	54.4	20	25.3

Table-8: Level of Satisfaction across disciplines

To test the difference (if any) regarding the satisfaction level for the resources and services provided by A.C. Joshi Library among the science and social science disciplines, independent

sample t -test has been applied as shown in Table-9 below. In the first stage, Library's efforts for both the disciplines were subjected to t -test, homogeneity of variances was assumed based on the Levene's test. Results show there is significant difference in the satisfaction level for social sciences and sciences faculties $t(150) = -1.050, p < 0.05$.

Discipline	n	Mean	SD	t-cal	df	p
Social Science	73	3.81	0.938	-1.050	150	.048
Science	79	3.96	0.869			

Table-9: t -test results for satisfaction level across discipline

3.2 Qualitative Narratives

The representation of faculty as indicated in Table-1 was asked to suggest other faculty members for the qualitative approach of data analysis. Apart from 152 respondents who had responded to online survey near about 25 more participants had responded to interview schedules making the total count as 55. The in-depth interviews with them also brought out varied responses. The responses were mixed, no doubt, but overall there was a renewed wave of awareness among the faculties of the available resources of the A.C. Joshi Library of the Panjab University. They are especially desirous of great inputs as is seen from their expectations which have been depicted as narratives for qualitative analysis or NQs.

NQ-I

“The need was for electronic access and that has been provided during this most difficult of times. There is an urgent need for improved remote access facility such as <https://technology.ku.edu/software/kuanystore> or Pulse which I have been using earlier during my stay abroad. India can compete with the best and A.C. Joshi Library should lead the way.”

NQ-II

“The university library should continue providing remote access facility to its faculty. In fact it should extend to research scholars as well. I extend our heartiest congratulation to the entire library staff. Thanks for providing e-material which was helpful in supplying study material to students, otherwise taking classes would not have been possible.”

NQ-III

“Along with e-mails I am highly appreciative of the personal telephonic information by the departmental librarian. Would greatly appreciate if the remote service being offered to the teaching fraternity is constant from now onwards. If possible, please subscribe to Endnote for the reference management. The library is doing a great job. Currently, there is greater access to more

e-books and journals. They are doing very well keeping the university library updated regularly, all the while being well-equipped with modern technology and services”.

NQ-IV

“The library should share such resources with the students also especially providing the facility of anti-plagiarism softwares too. These days the University library is playing a dynamic and cardinal role in online accessing of various online resources for faculty members, research scholars and students. However, in the coming days also once the COVID-19 situation normalizes the services should be continued for all the members of the university. Also the library must keep updating regularly”.

NQ-V

“Access of ACS e-journals must also be provided. It would be very wonderful if all CMIE databases, CEIS databases are made available. It should be made possible to download and send some standard text books through emails. The library should continue to provide most of these services even after the lockdown and post Lockdown phases, even when things go back to normal. It is a great experience of browsing and learning anywhere, anytime. The A.C. Joshi Library of the Panjab University is doing amazingly exemplary work. It will be good if Panjabstat.com is also subscribed, if possible all of us scholars who are stranded in our hometowns because of the COVID-19 pandemic are grateful to you for creating such a great resource. This facility, however, should be available continuously”.

NQ-VI

“The dedicated COVID-19 Library webpage consolidating all updates which is now disseminated via email/WA in a random manner should be regularized. Library Research Support (LRS/RSS) as also IR and RDM initiatives should be continued in the remote access areas. In fact the library should continue with more such kind of activities”.

NQ-VII

“The services being offered by the library are commendable but these are contingent upon the availability of infrastructure like a desktop and internet connectivity to begin with which may not be available with all faculty members. In my case I find it particularly cumbersome to log in using the official email, the functioning of which is extremely erratic. So I do think the library is providing enough resources provided one has the wherewithal to use these. I would like that the library should keep on sharing developments because even after lockdown the access to all such resources would be available from home itself. Therefore, please do enhance the availability of the library resources”.

NQ-VIII

“No email of password for e-resources has been received yet... hope it will reach soon... Please do send updates about books journals and webinars etc on Whatsapp alongwith E-books. I am sure more resources will be available in the near future for teaching and research purposes because full support of online journals and hard copy are required urgently by all academicians as teaching and learning practices have changed drastically. More reputed journals should be available and opening these to students as well should be considered to make them more accessible”. It would be good to have an open access to all journals not only at departmental level but anywhere where we may be located. A separate ID for each department should bring out this change. Please assure to continue such services uninterruptedly. It would be great to have better access to Medicine Journals like NEJM, Lancet, MCNA etc”.

NQ-IX

“Links are not opening properly through the Panjab University wifi. It would be good to develop best evaluation platforms. I would prefer the subject Approach to Information, which is missing right now. Make more resources available not only for faculties but also for students. Develop Zoom app like software. If on line mode of teaching has to succeed practically in India, then net connectivity to all parts of India needs to improve. Also there is a vital need to organize online training sessions on library resources and open source softwares with prime focus on secured softwares only”.

NQ-X

“Access should be made more Users friendly. At first we did not know how to use. We were simply provided with login id and password but had to constantly ask for instructions. We would greatly appreciate some more useful online resources specifically related to practicals which are the basic need in the life sciences. There is a need for training the faculty for optimization of resources. Kindly make us aware of facilities being provided. Please provide off campus facility even after the current situation tides over. There is a need to conduct frequent training and awareness workshops on these aspects. Please get the library to upload some more online training and videos related to library use, manuals etc on AC Joshi portal. It is necessary to make more of full text articles regarding medical and dental health available online. Self study modules for students are also required. I think I do not need anything else. Maybe some more resources can be added. The library should provide their best resources online because the digital library will be more effective in coming days. Therefore, it is necessary to make more online and digital sources available. I feel the AC Joshi Library always does the best possible and I am sure it will definitely in future also, no doubt, thanks please. The Library should include e-books of different subjects like those pertaining to the hospitality industry and tourism. Kindly allow teachers to the access library and provide them computer and other electronic source so that we can teach our students by using library books and other material. Kindly allow teacher to visit library 10 am to 5 pm. Most of the teachers need books to teach through online classes. Even net facility is limited (1GB or 2GB per day) and is very poor at their respective homes. Kindly allow teachers to visit library so that we

can teach through better speed of internet data speed. Latest books and all the reference material or its condensed form (digest) digest should be available in electronic form as well”.

NQ-XI

“Add e- content for law students. We can improve it by increasing more access for new sources and it should be available for scholars and researchers also. The library is making the best efforts. Workshops should be organized by A.C. Joshi related to plagiarism, research paper writing, accessing of E-resource, etc. Hope that the remote login facility is continues to be open even after the lockdown and post COVID-19 period. It should become an efficient study source through electronic media. Online access with more journal and e-books is required. The library already is doing excellent work. It should also provide the list of latest Edition of e-books of the respective syllabus. A webinar or e-workshop should be organized periodically to explain how to use e-resources from home. The arrangement of books which are in our library should be made available by online request system. The university library has already done what is desired to be done but it would be better if the resources are categorized as per the subjects. More remoteXs is required. It is better if these resources are available even beyond this extraordinary situation. The services to students and faculty must be extended in various modes under all circumstances.

NQ-XII

“Library is trying hard to keep us updated about the new resources. We needed authentic platform for teaching and discussion. I believe it is trying to work on providing more facilities. Keep up the good work. It would be good to have access to the PhD thesis submitted at the University, JSTOR etc. The library services are quite satisfactory. I would suggest that they make available discipline-wise e-books, access to Scifinder, more e-journals of repute, need for specialization specific access. There is requirement for online syllabus books, more databases to be added, to utilize online resources effectively post lockdown and to obtain information on the availability of resource. Let’s hope similar access will be available in the future as well. I expect that the university library should be able to help students with some online study material since most of them are at their respective homes. The online books availability and book search facility should be easily accessible. We should be able to subscribe Elsevier journals. Otherwise I am satisfied and hope that the library will continue the facilities being provided during lockdown.”

NQ-XIII

“Subscription of big data bases, more e-journal and books provisioning of database for Indian companies. Thank you for your continuous support, yet I feel more books should be available on-line; teachers should be acquainted with online books regularly. More resources are required in faculty of engineering and technology which can be explored by the users. There is a need for the addition of more and more e-books along with the addition of journals. I feel there needs to be more accessibility through online means”. Remote access should be continued after the lockdown

period also. Sometime, access of e-materials is not accessible. It should be made easily accessible. The Turnitin software and Science Direct subscription is a must for users like us”.

NQ-XIV

“We would like to see more e-journals in philosophy. In fact all e-books and e-journals should be made available. This is just a suggestion that university library should provide a social space for interaction and knowledge exchange which could probably be quiet good space for contemplation, a space for innovation which could be a neutral and trusted space for public use. There is need for the availability of material related to the performing arts”.

NQ-XV

“I am quite satisfied. It is good that access can be available to the faculty members even after office hours for carrying out research work. Even late night hours are becoming crucial for studies. It would be good to have access to data sources to which departments have subscribed like prowess database. It is a must to provide access to all Indian and Scopus listed Journals. Some suggestions from me are:

- 1. The Library must develop a COVID information portal*
- 2. All the emails and sources should be merged in single copy and organized according to subject instead of multiple emails through cc.*
- 3. Providing solutions to online teaching should be a priority”.*

NQ-XVI

“Even good facility for plagiarism check is not available. Must try to get all the e-journals. To able to continue their present work the teaching faculty must be provided user friendly access to e-resources and to also include more resources as per requirement of various research scholars and researchers. RemoteXs facility should continue as it is an easy approach”.

Thus, from the qualitative assessment of the views of the teaching faculty, it is apparent that there is a broad concern on the part of the academicians to be able to prepare themselves adequately. Undercurrents of stress have palpated their anxiety to ensure they are well-versed with the latest technological advancements to be able to satisfy their students. The constant worry and confusion was beginning to tell on their socio-psychological well being. Many of them have reported feeling overwhelmed as they try to keep up with their teaching in these challenging circumstances. For those who participated in online teaching for the first time, there was an added strain of having to learn a whole new way of working. Online resources were available, but not all teacher learners had the conditions to work with such resources due to non-availability of suitable study area, Internet access, etc. In this environment of increased pressure, faculty is moving into a new mode of what has been termed “pedagogy of care”.

4. Conclusions

The study shows that there has been a large amount of widespread confusion among the teaching faculty at Panjab University. There were several queries on the usage of technologies for accessing library information, the quality of information available and that which was required seemed to present a mismatch and in several places wide gap was visualized. Moreover, this gap is affecting their physical and mental stress. Many of them had reported certain psychological symptoms like anxiety, tension, confusion, anger besides depression during the interview schedules.

Based on the responses of the users the main findings were:

1. There was large-scale insecurity and confusion regarding the usage of the library resources.
2. Some logged through ID and password but had difficulty obtaining the desired inputs
3. Great difficulty was faced by the teaching faculty of all subjects in accessing relevant teaching material.
4. The younger faculty members managed to adapt themselves to the newer scenario, while the senior members were dependent upon others.
5. Assistant Professor level faculty of the Panjab University want the accessibility of library resources to continue beyond the lockdown period as well.

Thus, while there was large scale dissatisfaction with the situation when gates of libraries were closed during the lockdown period, tremendous stress was being experienced by majority of the users of the academic libraries for carrying out their teaching assignments especially as they were unable to use the available facilities to their total need and satisfaction. On the other hand, those who managed to access the facilities had several reservations about the quantum and content of the resources being shared by them. Hence, there are severe policy implications of the kind of stress that is being faced by the academicians who were carrying with the additional burden of teaching without having physical access to libraries. Several academicians have given the plea to be able to access more resources than were already available while many of them wanted their students also to be able to access the facilities available to them so that they could synchronize resources available. However, it was also observed that the electronic resources and services being provided by A.C. Joshi Library in the current pandemic scenario are indispensable. It's active and dynamic role in providing easy access to authoritative information at right time and disseminating in proper format has acted as a panacea to some extent to academicians in coping with mental stress.

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